

CAMELINA SATIVA PROTOCOL FOR INTRODUCTION AS AN AUTUMN CROP FOR DOUBLE CROPPING IN ITALY

INTRODUCTION

Camelina can be introduced in farmer rotations as an autumn intermediate crop preceding summer main crop such as sorghum, soybean or sunflower in Italian regions where double cropping is feasible. The present protocol, optimized within the UNTWIST project through three years of field experiments in northern Italy, addresses the introduction of camelina as an autumn intermediate crop for double cropping.

FACTS

- **Common names:** Camelina, Leindotter, Gold of Pleasure, False Flax.
- **Scientific name:** *Camelina sativa* (L.) Crantz
Family: Brassicaceae or Cruciferae.
- **Drought-resistant oil crop** with a yield potential of 2.5 t/ha.
- **Plant height:** 60 to 120 cm.
- **Pollinator friendly species.**
- **1000-seed weight:** 0.8 - 1.6 g.

ADVANTAGES

- **Conventional machinery for winter cereals.**
- **Easy implementation & low-input crop.**
- **Drought & frost tolerant.**
- **Catch crop.**
- **Pest & disease tolerant.**
- **Pivoting root** - soil structure improver.
- **Fit for autumn, winter and early spring sowing.**
- **Suitable summer crops** after camelina harvest: soybean, sunflower.

AGRONOMIC PROTOCOL KEY POINTS

PLOTS

Avoid easily waterlogged soils, with crust formation and pH less than 5.5 and greater than 8.5.

SOWING

Shallow sowing (≈ 1 cm) in rows (13-17 cm distance) on a plot without weeds or straw.

NUTRIENTS

Guarantee minimum nitrogen availability including soil N (100 kg N/ha).

HERBICIDES

Resistant to many grass-killer but susceptible to dicot herbicides.

CAMELINA SATIVA PROTOCOL

FOR INTRODUCTION AS AN AUTUMN CROP FOR DOUBLE CROPPING IN ITALY

SOWING	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Sowing date: Autumn (last two weeks of October - first two weeks of November).▪ Sowing rate: 5-6 kg/ha.▪ Row sowing: 13-17 cm between rows.▪ Sowing depth: Superficially \approx 1 cm. Ensure a good seed-soil contact.▪ Roll before sowing, if needed.▪ Fertilization: Guarantee minimum nitrogen availability (100 kg N/ha).
WEEDS	<p>Check soil N availability before sowing. Apply N fertilizer at rosette stage to reach in total max 100 kg N/ha. Excessive fertilization decreases seed oil content and causes lodging problems. With a proper crop establishment, camelina competes well with weeds (allelopathic effect). Check the herbicides registered for narrowleaf control in your country.</p>
HARVEST	<p>Between end of May until mid June, when the siliques have turned from lemon yellow to brown, seeds should be light brown. Do not wait until basal part of the plant is dry, it will be too late. Combine setting: i) Raise the cutting bar to the height of the first fruits (10-15 cm from the soil) and lower rpm; ii) Set the combine for small seed harvest; iii) Reduce to minimum the ventilation in the sieve and straw separation system.</p>
POST-HARVEST	<p>Maximum moisture for storage: 8 %. If an excess of moisture is detected in the harvested grain (symptom: heating), pre-cleaning and eventually drying is recommended.</p>

Sowing date, sowing rate and strategy as well as nitrogen fertilization rate was optimized in 3-year field trials within the **UNTWIST project**. The other parts of the protocol are based on previous experience with the crop and other projects and research work.

STAGES IN CAMELINA PRODUCTION

Photographs provided by Camelina Company.